

Karapan Sapi: The Implementation of Madura's Culture as an English Learning Medium

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Abstract

This article discusses the application of the Karapan Sapi culture as a medium of learning English at the primary school level. This research aims to explore the potential of using local culture as an effective means of teaching English to young students. The research method used is the development and implementation of learning programs that integrate the cultural elements of the Madura Cow Carpentry, including traditions, values, and related skills. This article provides an overview of the implementation results, their impact on students' motivation and understanding of English, as well as recommendations for further development in the context of local culture-based English teaching in primary schools. The results of this research are expected to contribute positively to the approach to learning English at the primary level through the use of local cultures as an attractive and relevant learning medium for students.

Keywords: Karapan Sapi, Madura's Culture, English Learning Medium

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Introduction

English is an international language that is often used by many people to interact with or communicate with other people in various parts of the world (Rao, 2019). One of the foreign languages most widely used to interact with other people is English (Lestari & Wahyudin, 2020). English is the language that has the most speakers, also known as *Lingua Franca* (Kirkpatrick & Schaller-Schwane, 2022). Acquiring proficiency in the English language is an exceedingly crucial endeavor. Given the current state of our modern society and the intense level of competition, it is widely assumed that individuals possess not only a high level of education but also specialized abilities, sometimes referred to as "skills." Fluency in English is considered a crucial talent in today's world. In order to effectively communicate on a global scale, it is essential to actively acquire proficiency in English, encompassing both oral and writing skills. According to Ki Hajar Dewantara Education, education is a guide in the life of children's growth (Bustomi et al., 2022), meaning that education guides all the natural strengths that exist in children (Frank et al., 2021), so that they, as humans and as members of society, can achieve the highest safety and happiness. Education is an activity in

the form of learning, knowledge, and skills that occurs in the school room in order to develop oneself and can produce changes in attitudes so that they become better. As we know, we have undergone various educations in the school environment, starting from PAUD, elementary school, middle school, high school, and undergraduate education. To increase student effectiveness, game-based learning media are used here. Children have an amazing ability to absorb language through play and other activities that they find enjoyable (Sahlberg & Doyle, 2019). So from the explanations above, we can use media that as an interesting to children in the form of games, videos, pictures, and others that can make students not easily feel bored when learning, because when the teacher provides media that can make students interested, then the students will be more active in studying it. The definition of media in the teaching and learning process tends to be interpreted as graphic (Burbules et al., 2020), photographic, or electronic tools to capture, process, and reconstruct visual or verbal information (Haris Budiman et al., 2016). Media are people, materials, or events that create conditions that enable students to acquire knowledge, skills, or attitudes (Aslan et al., 2020). The various types of media in learning can be visual media, audio media, and audio-visual media (Sarwinda et al., 2020). So here we can use media that can make students interested in learning, whether in the form of game-based learning media or others.

Game-based learning media is an educational approach that use games to facilitate learning and enhance students' engagement. Its purpose is to cultivate students' interest in learning, preventing them from experiencing boredom during both in-class and out-of-class learning activities. Game-based learning is associated with Madurese culture, specifically with the traditional sport of "Karapan Sapi." This game involves the presentation of multiple images associated with "Karapan Sapi," prompting students to identify the objects depicted. The objective is to enhance students' vocabulary and speaking skills. Cow racing, known as Karapan Sapi, is a highly skilled and artistic competition where cows compete against each other. This approach emphasizes the prioritization of oral communication abilities by researchers. According to (Gangal, 2012), Speaking is the capacity to articulate phonetic sounds or words in order to communicate thoughts, concepts, and emotions. Speaking is the act of expressing oneself through verbal communication, involving the use of words, conversation, and dialogue with others. The objective of verbal communication in this context is to cultivate students' ability to articulate the substance of their thoughts without experiencing any inhibitions in sharing their viewpoints with others. Elementary education serves as the foundation for acquiring essential knowledge that students must possess, including the acquisition of English language skills. (Sepyanda, 2017). Students are now

being provided with educational resources on foreign languages to facilitate communication with individuals from different regions of the world. The objective is for students to acquire proficiency in English, enabling them to effectively represent their nation, particularly in the realm of language. The primary school where I performed my research is SDN Prekbun, situated in Pademawu, Pamekasan Regency, a considerable distance away from urban regions. The study focused on the elementary school of SDN Prekbun due to the researcher's limited proficiency in English. The objective of this study is to incorporate the "Karapan" Madurese cow culture, with a particular focus on its potential benefits for English language acquisition. The objective of this lesson is to present a video or photo of "Karapan sapi" and prompt the students to carefully observe and explain the visual elements depicted in the image. Through the utilization of this approach, students will engage in more active verbal communication, thereby enhancing their proficiency. By employing this approach, students will be less prone to boredom and will experience a renewed sense of enjoyment in their studies. This research is highly valuable for teachers and students as it facilitates the teaching process by incorporating the visual medium of "Karapan Sapi," a cultural practice in Madura, into English language learning. In addition to integrating this cultural aspect, teachers can utilize activities shown in images. The objective of this study is to enhance students' engagement in oral communication in the English language. For researchers and external entities, this study provides valuable insights into the ability of rural schools to communicate in English, despite facing delays in accessing up-to-date information in the field of education.

Research Method

This type of research is included in qualitative research (Sepyanda, 2017). Data analysis activities using qualitative research are carried out by searching for data and arranging it systematically in relation to what is obtained by grouping, describing, synthesizing, arranging patterns, selecting what is important, and drawing conclusions from field data (Nassaji, 2015). This qualitative research is very suitable to be carried out in the research to be conducted because it discusses how the Karapan Sapi as a culture and a medium for learning English.

a. Research Scope or Objectives

SDN Prekbun is an elementary school situated in a remote village, distant from the urban area. The school comprises six classes, however, this research will specifically concentrate on class 4. This study will specifically examine students' speaking proficiency

and pronunciation. Regarding the utilization of the English language, as well as the circumstances inside the classroom setting.

b. Research Tools and Primary Data

The instrument in this research uses tests on students about what the researcher examines, such as observing students' attitudes during the teaching and learning process, asking questions to students after receiving learning material, and giving tests to students to measure students' abilities. understanding of the material that has been presented.

c. Research Setting

The classroom environment or conditions at SDN Prekbun, particularly in grade 4, are still unfavorable due to kids' inadequate understanding of English language instruction. During the learning process, students refrain from speaking and instead focus on listening if they have already grasped the lesson. However, when faced with challenges in learning, particularly in the context of English language acquisition, students tend to disregard listening and choose for self-expression through talking. Therefore, it can be inferred that students' learning outcomes are influenced by the effectiveness of the teacher's explanations and their ability to employ engaging instructional methods that prevent student disinterest during classroom instruction. By employing game-based learning techniques, the Karapan Sapi culture serves as a platform for English language acquisition. In this approach, I will present an image or video of a cow, and thereafter prompt students to identify the objects depicted in the visual using the English language.

d. Data collection technique

To obtain accurate and accountable data for the research being studied, the researcher used data collection techniques consisting of:

1. Observation is a data collection technique that involves observing and recording (Barker, 1980). The researcher examines the deficiencies and progress of the target of study by observing the actualities and facts present in the field or school being investigated. The researcher personally conducted an assessment in the classroom to evaluate the students' auditory perception and lexical knowledge.
2. An interview is a conversation between two or more people and occurs between the source and the interviewer (Warren, 2002). In this instance, the researcher conducted direct interviews with both the principal and the English teacher to ascertain the school's conditions and the proficiency level of the pupils in English.
3. Documentation is a record of events that occurred in the past (Bearman, 1992). The documentation provided consists of written or visual materials. Researchers utilize

this documentation to record and present the findings of their field or academic study.

e. Data analysis technique

Researchers conducted data analysis upon the completion of the teaching and learning procedure. This data analysis was conducted to assess the efficacy and deficiencies of the pedagogical process in educational institutions, the coherence of utilizing instructional materials or media, and the diverse challenges encountered in both classroom and extracurricular learning environments. Through this observation or research, we aim to address all issues present in the teaching and learning process in order to identify solutions for each problem. Additionally, this evaluation will enhance the implementation of learning and the teaching and learning process. Put simply, the deficiencies identified in this observation can be utilized to forecast the approach and effectiveness of the teaching and learning process on the following day. Through this assessment, the learning experience can be enhanced compared to the previous day.

Finding and Discussion

During the research conducted at Prekbun Elementary School, particularly in class 4, researchers made numerous significant discoveries. The class comprised 11 pupils, with 6 being male and 5 being female. Another observation revealed that the classroom or media equipment available to facilitate learning was in excellent condition. The classroom was equipped with study tables and chairs for both students and teachers, as well as fans, projectors, and designated reading areas. The conditions for the students were highly favorable and easily manageable due to their strong interest in the media, which the researcher utilized in performing the study. This section will examine students who exhibit varying levels of receptiveness towards English language learning, specifically focusing on their acceptance or non-acceptance. The study will explore the use of the Madurese cultural cow race as a medium for English language learning in SDN Prekbun.

The Classifications of Student's Response

Students	Students Response				Arguments
	Very Accept	Accept	Middle	Unaccepted	
Aikatul Jannah	✓				They were very receptive
Putri Oktaviany	✓				

Sugianto					and able to
Moh . Nofal	✓				use English because they had previously taken English lessons outside of school.
PrasitiyoWilli Kurniawan		✓			This student was able to
Moh . Fahri Mustofa		✓			accept learning English because he was interested in the media I used, namely "Karapan Sapi Vidio, or pictures." And coincidentally , this student liked the Karapan Sapi culture, so even though he was not fluent in learning English, he still tried
Naura Azdqia				✓	This student

Barera					is still not used to using English because he is still not fluent in reading and cannot even read, so he finds it difficult to carry out learning, including learning English.
Ahmad Frenki Safari Adit Putra			✓		These students are still new to using English, and they still experience a little difficulty in learning it. but he could know a little of the vocabulary used in Karapan Sapi.
Syafira Agustina Ramadhani		✓			Students accept. even though he is still in the

					stage of learning English, because according to him, learning English is very difficult but important. So even though he is not very proficient in English, he still tries to learn it, and according to him, learning English will definitely be needed one day.
Syafira Febriana Arrahmah		✓			Three students accepted because, when asked about what objects were in the media, they could answer. However, there is one word that is
Moh . Faris Alfarisi		✓			
Rafasya Rakha Pratama		✓			

					said to be foreign or new, such as the word "tongar."
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During the implementation of the Cow Method in class 4 at SDN Prekbun to enhance English language acquisition, some students encountered both failures and successes due to various factors. Among the 11 students, who had multiple justifications, including:

- a. Three pupils who possess a high level of English proficiency due to their prior experience in taking English courses outside of school.
- b. Two pupils embraced English language learning due to their keen interest in the medium I employed, specifically the "Karapan Sapi video or pictures." Furthermore, it is worth noting that this particular student had a keen interest in the Karapan Sapi culture. Despite not being proficient in English, he made a sincere effort to learn.
- c. One student lacks proficiency in English, as she is not yet proficient in reading and struggles with comprehension, making it challenging for her to engage in learning activities, including English language acquisition.
- d. Two pupils have limited proficiency in English; they have certain challenges in acquiring English language skills. However, he may possess a limited understanding of the terminology employed in Karapan Sapi.
- e. Three students were accepted based on their ability to accurately identify objects in the media when questioned. Nevertheless, there exists a word that is commonly regarded as foreign or novel, such as the term "tongar." They are unaware of it. Furthermore, they believe that this is one of the consequences of online education as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, which has made learning less favourable, particularly in the subject of English.
- f. One student agrees. Despite being in the early stages of studying English, he acknowledges that mastering the language is challenging yet crucial. Despite his limited English proficiency, he remains committed to learning the language, as he believes that mastering English will inevitably become necessary in the future.

The investigation was conducted at SD Prekbun, located in Pademawu District, Pamekasan Regency. Utilizing the cow race image as a means to enhance English proficiency,

we can deduce that employing this method as a tool for English learning is highly effective and fruitful. It has proven to enhance students' English abilities, encompassing vocabulary and understanding. Students communicate using the English language.

Conclusion

Indonesia is a culturally diverse country that encompasses numerous livestock cultures. Karapan Sapi is a manifestation of Madurese art that serves as a cultural production. Karapan Sapi is an attraction rooted in Madurese culture, where cow racing competitions are showcased as a distinct embodiment of this cultural tradition. The researcher did a study on cultural nuances as a means to enhance English language acquisition, with the aim of preserving our culture from fading away. Utilizing Karapan Sapi Culture as a platform for English language instruction enables us to enhance students' vocabulary and oral communication skills, fostering greater engagement and self-assurance. Based on this study, we may deduce that acquiring proficiency in the English language is a really straightforward endeavour. This phenomenon is seen in the aforementioned research. Consequently, pupils' comprehension of the information will be facilitated if they possess a genuine interest in the media employed. When students have a sense of curiosity, comprehending our message becomes effortless, and they are less prone to becoming disinterested during the learning process.

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